

STUDIES ON THE ESSENTIAL OIL FROM THE RHIZOME OF *ACORUS CALAMUS*. PART I. ISOLATION AND EXAMINATION OF CALAMOL.

BY MUHAMMAD QUDRAT-I-KHUDA, ASUTOSH MUKHERJEE AND
SUBASH KUMAR GHOSH.

From the rhizome of *Acorus calamus*, an oily substance, calamol ($C_{12}H_{18}O_8$) has been extracted. It is found to be an allyltrimethoxybenzene derivative and it yields a tetrabromo derivative. Calamol by the action of alkali isomerises into isocalamol, both the isomers yielding on oxidation the same calamonic acid ($C_{10}H_{12}O_5$), a trimethoxybenzoic acid, isomeric with asaronic, trimethoxypyrogallic or trimethylgallic acid, but not identical with any of them.

The European variety of acorus has been examined by various workers with different results. In the present investigation the rhizomes of the variety locally known as "ghore bacha" has been used.

Kurbatow (*Ber.*, 1873, 6, 1210) distilled an oil from *Acorus calamus* and considered it to be $C_{10}H_{18}$. Von Soden and Rajahn (*Pharm. Z.*, 1901, 46, 243) isolated a solid, calameon, ($C_{15}H_{26}O_2$) from the Galician root. Thoms and Beckstroem (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 1021; 1902, 35, 3187, 3195; *Ber. Phar. Ges.*, 1902, 12, 257) isolated asarone (m.p. 61°), asarylic aldehyde, eugenol, *n*-heptylic ester and some terpenes from the Japanese oil. Semmler and Spornitz (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 3700) examined the Russian oil from which they obtained pinene, camphene, camphor and also a sesquiterpene ($C_{15}H_{24}$). Schimmel & Co. determined the physical constants of the Japanese oil (Schimmel's Reports, April, 1909, p. 22). Russel (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 37, 2387) examined the oil obtained from the plants cultivated in Madison, Wisconsin.

Some work has also been done on the Indian Calamus oil. Rao, Sudborough and Watson (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1925, 8A, 149) obtained 1.5 to 3.5% of oil from the roots, procured from Coimbatore district, and determined its constants. In recent years Kelkar and Rao (*ibid.*, 1934, 17A, 25) described an oil obtained from *Acorus calamus* that contained such compounds as palmitic and heptoic acid, ester of palmitic acid together with some pinene, camphene, asaraldehyde, eugenol, asarone, calamene, calamenol and calameon. But the rhizome that we have used appears

to behave differently. It gives an oil that does not appear in any way similar to any of the substances mentioned above ; on the other hand it appears to be similar to some extent to the compound isolated by Rao and Subramanian (*Current Science*, 1935, 3, 552), but is not identical with it.

The oil isolated in a yield of about 8% of the dried root gives only one product which boils at almost a constant temperature and we could not isolate the fractions mentioned by Rao, Sudborough and Watson (*loc. cit.*) or by Kelkar and Rao (*loc. cit.*). To this compound, we have given the name "calamol".

Calamol is a colourless mobile liquid, with a strong characteristic and a rather pleasant aromatic odour. It does not show the presence of any acids, esters, etc. The M. W. and analytical values of the sample suggest its formula to be $C_{12}H_{16}O_3$. It is most probably a benzenoid compound, isomeric with asarone.

The oil is transformed into an isomeric substance when boiled with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and no trace of any acid could be isolated from the alkaline solution. This neutral oil has odour reminiscent of the aroma of "Bel fruits" (*Aegle marmelos*). We conclude that calamol is not an ester and it does not possess a carboxyl group, but is isomerised with alkali into *isocalamol*.

The ready absorption of bromine by the compound indicates the presence of an unsaturated group in the molecule. The bromo derivative could not be obtained pure, as it decomposes on distillation. An analysis of the crude bromo compound suggests it to be a tetrabromo derivative. In presence of palladium, calamol takes up two atoms of hydrogen and gives dihydrocalamol ($C_{12}H_{18}O_3$).

The original oil, calamol, can thus be written as

which changes into *isocalamol* $C_9H_{11}O_3 - CH = CH \cdot CH_3$.

Aluminium chloride decomposes calamol partially with the production of a phenolic compound of a characteristic phenolic odour. Methoxyl determination indicates three methoxyl groups in calamol, hence it is probably a trimethoxyallylbenzene.

*iso*Calamol also analyses for three methoxyl groups, therefore, the action of alkali is restricted to the allyl group of the molecule only.

Calamol on oxidation should give a trimethoxyphenylacetic acid, but when it is oxidised by potassium permanganate solution calamonic acid

(trimethoxybenzoic acid) is formed, the double bond being shifted by the alkali of the reaction mixture. The m.p. of the product precludes its being trimethoxypyrogallol carboxylic acid, trimethoxygallic acid, trimethylphloroglucinol carboxylic acid and 2:4:5-trimethoxybenzoic acid (asaronic acid).

It can be 2:4:6-trimethoxy- or 3:4:6-trimethoxybenzoic acid. On demethylation of the acid, a trihydroxybenzoic acid is obtained which melts at a temperature different from the m.p. of phloroglucinol carboxylic acid or 2:4:5-trihydroxybenzoic acid.

Therefore, the relative orientation of the the methoxy groups is probably 2:3:5 or 2:3:6 or 3:4:6. Experiments are now in progress to decide the question.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Extraction of Calamol from Ghore Bacha.—The rhizome as obtained from the market, without any dressing, was cut into very small pieces and crushed as fine as was practicable. The crushed rhizome (200 g.) was then mixed with 400 c.c. of water, and was distilled in steam for 6 hours (direct heating on a sand-bath should be avoided to prevent charring of the fibres) and the total amount of distillate collected was 7 litres. This was saturated with common salt and was extracted twice with ether. The ethereal extract was dried (fused calcium chloride) and the solvent removed. The residual oil was fractionally distilled under reduced pressure. Calamol had b.p. 153-54°/5 mm.

The following quantities of the oil were obtained from different experiments:

(i) From 1000 g., 80 g. (ii) from 1400 g., 108 g. (iii) from 1600 g., 125 g. (iv) from 1000 g., 81 g. of calamol were obtained, *i.e.* from a total quantity of 5000 g. of rhizome 394 g. of the essential oil were obtained constituting 7.88%.

The oil obtained as above was purified by several redistillations and the purest sample, b.p. 153-154°/5 mm., was analysed. [Found: C, 69.3; H, 8.3; M.W. (ebullioscopic method), 214. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7 per cent. M.W., 208]. [Found: OMe, 44.7. $C_9H_7(OMe)_3$ requires OMe, 44.7 per cent]. It had $d_4^{30.1}$, 1.07021; $n_D^{30.1}$, 1.55012; Found: $[R_L]_D$ 61.9 (calc. 58.5).

Conversion of Calamol into isoCalamol.—To a solution of potassium hydroxide (20 g.) in water (30 c.c.) was added calamol (20 g.) and enough rectified spirit (100 c.c.) to make a clear and homogeneous solution, which was then heated under reflux for about 10 hours and the alcohol was distilled off. The cooled mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The alkaline solution furnished nothing definite when acidified and extracted in the usual way. The ethereal extract was washed with water and then dried and distilled, b.p. $133^{\circ}/2$ mm. It possessed a very characteristic odour which was absolutely different from that of the original oil. [Found : C, 69.3 ; H, 7.8 ; OMe, 44.9 ; M. W. (cryoscopic), 208.1. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.2 ; H, 7.7 ; OMe (3 methoxyls), 44.9 per cent]. It had $d_4^{31.5}$, 1.07261 ; $n_D^{31.5}$, 1.55229 whence $[R_L]_D$, 61.85 (calc. 58.85).

Action of Bromine on Calamol.—Bromine was rapidly absorbed when a dry petroleum solution of bromine (1.5 g.) was added to a solution of calamol (3 g.) in the same solvent (100 c.c.). A heavy deeply coloured bromo compound separated out, the supernatant petroleum solution was removed and the coloured mass was taken up in ether and washed with a dilute solution of potassium hydroxide, charcoaled and filtered. The nearly colourless solution was freed from the solvent and the residual mass was left in *vacuo*, dark blue colour developing on standing. On distillation it rapidly decomposed and no definite compound could be isolated. The crude bromo compound was analysed after keeping in the desiccator for some time. [Found : Br (Piria and Schiff), 57.1. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3Br_4$ requires Br, 60.8 per cent].

Catalytic Hydrogenation of Calamol.—Calamol (22 g.) in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) was reduced with 1% palladium chloride (50 c.c.) containing gum arabic (10 c.c. of 5%) when the absorption was quite rapid in the beginning, 2.5 litres of hydrogen being absorbed in about $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The reaction was carried on for $5\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The mixture was diluted with water till turbid and then extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with water and dried (calcium chloride) and solvent removed. Dihydrocalamol boiled at $124^{\circ}/2$ mm. (yield 20 g.). (Found : C, 68.72 ; H, 8.72. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.6 ; H, 8.6 per cent). It had $d_4^{31.2}$, 1.03109 ; $n_D^{31.2}$, 1.51219 whence $[R_L]_D$, 61.1 (calc. 58.0).

Demethylation of Calamol (a) Demethylation with Aluminium Chloride.—Calamol (20 g.), dissolved in dry petroleum ether (100 c.c., b.p. $50-70^{\circ}$) was demethylated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (20 g.) at 100° for 5

hours. The cooled mass was extracted with petrol, solvent was removed and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure. The phenolic compound had b.p. $115^{\circ}/2$ mm. (Found : C, 68.1, H, 8.37. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 68.04 ; H, 7.2 per cent). Hence it seems that aluminium chloride causes partial demethylation, only one methoxyl group being lost.

(b) *Demethylation with Hydriodic Acid.*—For complete demethylation calamol (10 g.) was heated with hydriodic acid (d 1.7) for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours at $115-120^{\circ}$. The cooled mixture was thoroughly extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed first with water, then with a little dilute solution of sodium thiosulphate and finally with water. After drying over sodium sulphate and the removal of solvent a black tarry residue remained which could not be purified by charcoaling in ethereal solution. It was extracted with water and then kept in contact with animal charcoal for some time. After the removal of water under reduced pressure, only a small quantity of an oily residue was obtained. The oil decomposed on distillation under reduced pressure (2 mm.). It was, therefore, benzoylated in the usual way and a solid substance was obtained which was purified by crystallisation from dilute rectified spirit. After several crystallisations, it had m.p. 96° . (Found : C, 75.0 ; H, 4.1. $C_{30}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 75.3 ; H, 4.6 per cent).

Oxidation of Calamol : Preparation of Calamonic Acid.—A mixture of calamol (25 g.) sodium hydroxide solution (400 c.c. of 10%) was oxidised with the gradual addition of a solution of potassium permanganate (140 g.) in water (3500 c.c.) with stirring for 6 hours and then the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The clear filtrate was concentrated on a water-bath till crystallisation set in. A thick flocculent precipitate, obtained by acidification with hydrochloric acid, was crystallised from hot water in fine colourless needles, m. p. 143° . [Found : C, 56.3 ; H, 5.6 ; OMe, 41.36. M.W. (by titration), 211.8. $C_{10}H_{12}O_5$ or $C_8H_2(OMe)_3COOH$ requires C, 56.6 ; H, 5.6 ; OMe, 41.3 per cent. M.W. 212].

*iso*Calamol was also oxidised under condition exactly similar to that described above and gave the same compound, with identical m.p. and mixed m.p.

Demethylation of Calamonic Acid : Preparation of Trihydroxybenzoic Acid.—The foregoing trimethoxybenzoic acid (10 g.) was heated with hydriodic acid (d , 1.7) under conditions similar to those described above in the case of the allyl compound when crystalline solid, mixed with some oily and coloured impurities, was obtained. After draining on a porous plate, the

acid was crystallised from a mixture of dry ether and petrol in the colourless form, m.p. 97° . (Found . C, 49.2 ; H, 3.6. $C_7H_6O_2$ requires C, 49.4 ; H, 3.6 per cent).

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ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

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